

ACOUSTIC EMISSION DETECTION AND PREDICTION OF FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION IN COMPOSITE PATCH REPAIRS USING NEURAL NETWORKS

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SUMMARY: Composite patch repairs are increasingly used to repair damaged aircraft metallic structures. This calls for a reliable method for assessing the integrity of bonded repairs and detecting crack propagation after patch repair without stripping the repair. This paper presents the results of Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring of cracked 2024-T3 clad aluminum panels repaired with adhesively bonded octagonal and elliptical single sided boron/epoxy composite patches under tension-tension fatigue loading. Two crack propagation gages and four AE sensors were used to monitor crack initiation and propagation respectively. AE signals were acquired and processed in time and frequency domain to identify sensor features correlated with fatigue cycle and crack propagation. Methods for AE noise reduction, accurate source location, and crack length prediction are presented. The results show that AE events and fatigue cycles are correlated with crack propagation. The identified sensor features were used to train three back-propagation feed forward neural networks to predict crack length based on the number of fatigue cycles, AE event number, and fatigue cycles with AE events together, as inputs. It was found that network with fatigue cycles as input gave better results than network with just AE events as input. However the network using both fatigue cycles and AE event number as inputs gave best results.

Keywords: Composite patch repair; Aging aircraft; Acoustic Emission; Adhesively Bonded composite patches; Fatigue; Crack growth; Artificial Neural Networks

1. INTRODUCTION

The high acquisition costs associated with the purchase of modern aircrafts, military as well as commercial, coupled with the existing economic and market forces have resulted in the utilization of aircrafts beyond their original design life. Due to extended service life of aircrafts many military and commercial aircrafts have suffered structural damage from fatigue, stress corrosion and hence maintenance or repair has become an important issue in recent years.

The technique of repairing cracked metallic aircraft structures using high strength advanced composite materials is commonly known as “Crack Patching,” which was pioneered by the Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratories (AMRL), for the Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF), in early 1970s[1]. The composite reinforcement, also known as a patch, can be attached to the damaged or weakened structure either by mechanical fastener or adhesive bonding. The use of adhesively bonded composite patches as a method of repair has several advantages over mechanically fastened repair methods, which include reduced installation cost, increased strength and fatigue life, and hence effective crack retardation, reduced repair down time, and elimination of unnecessary fastener holes in an already weakened structure.

Development of a reliable Non-Destructive Testing and Evaluation (NDT&E) method for detection of crack initiation and propagation is very closely related to assessing the integrity of structures. Acoustic emission (AE) testing is one of the most popular and widely used methods of NDT&E and is amenable to real time monitoring of fatigue crack growth. Acoustic emission signals are high frequency transient stress waves produced by rapid release of energy from localized sources that travel through the material. During fatigue crack propagation a portion of the strain energy released by the growing crack is transmitted through the parent material as acoustic emission signal. These AE waves can be detected by broadband high fidelity AE sensors attached to the specimen, and can be digitized for analysis purposes.

The difference between the AE testing technique and other NDT&E methods is that AE detects the activities inside the materials, while other NDT&E methods attempt to examine the internal structures of the materials. Other NDT&E methods, such as ultrasonic, eddy current, and x-ray, require scanning the whole structure or specimen, and therefore, the structure or specimen often needs to be disassembled and taken to the laboratory to be examined when damage areas are inaccessible to these techniques. This is a very expensive proposition, especially if no defects are found. Also these techniques can miss flaws if the orientation of the flaw does not interact with the ultrasonic beam or the eddy current field. Thus the use of multiple testing techniques might be appropriate.

The disadvantage of AE testing is that commercial AE systems can only estimate qualitatively how much damage is in the material. So, other NDT&E methods are still needed to do more detailed examinations and provide quantitative results. Moreover, in-service environments are generally very noisy, and the AE signals are usually very weak. Thus, signal discrimination and noise reduction are very difficult, yet extremely important for successful AE applications.

This paper presents the results of Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring of cracked 2024-T3 Clad aluminum panels repaired with adhesively bonded octagonal and elliptical single sided boron/epoxy composite patches under tension-tension fatigue loading. Crack propagation and initiation was monitored using AE signals and analyzed to develop a correlation between crack propagation and AE events, and fatigue cycles. Crack initiation was monitored using crack propagation gage and crack propagation monitored using Acoustic Emission sensors. Three back-propagation neural network models were developed and used to predict crack length from AE events and fatigue cycles as inputs to the network. A methodology for noise reduction, accurate source location and crack length prediction is presented.

2. DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF PATCH

2.1 Patch Design

The composite patches used in this research were designed using the CRAS® v0.3 [2] developed by the United States Air Force. CRAS stands for Composite Repair of Aircraft Structures. The patches were designed for a single sided repair of a 1 inch crack on a 15 x 3x 0.063 inch sheet of 2024-T3 clad aluminum. The design of the patch was for a maximum uniaxial stress of $\sigma_{yy} = 40.5$ ksi with 150,000 cycles of fatigue loading at a uniaxial stress of $\sigma_{yy} = 13.5$ ksi. The details of the design procedure and the various considerations for designing a composite patch are presented in a previous work of the authors [3].

2.2 Machining of Aluminum Panels

2024-T3 Clad aluminum panels were machined to a dog-bone shape as shown in Figure 1a, on Cincinnati Milacron SABRE-750 Vertical Machining Center. The aluminum was

machined such that the grain direction was aligned with the loading axis. The dimensions of the panels were 3 x 0.063 inch in cross-section and length of 15 inch. A central through crack of 1 inch was machined by a wire EDM. A small hole of 0.02 inch at the center was drilled first for the EDM wire to go through.

2.3 Fabrication of Patches

Figure 1b shows the placement of the composite patches on the pre-cracked aluminum panels. The composite patch is made from boron/epoxy 5521 prepreg (Textron Specialty Materials Inc.) with a uni-directional lay-up of $[0]_n$ (where n is the number of plies), with fibers oriented in the direction of loading. The patches were applied to the aluminum panel using FM-73 (Cytac Fiberite.) adhesive. The surfaces of the aluminum panels were prepared before placing on the patch, by degreasing the aluminum panels with acetone followed by grit blasting and application of a primer. The primer was applied to prevent oxidation before placing the patch.

The curing conditions for boron/epoxy require the temperature to ramped up at a rate of 3 – 5° F/min to 250° F and soaking at this temperature for 60 minutes at a pressure of 50 – 85 psi followed by a ramping down at 8° F/min. The curing cycle for FM-73 requires the temperature to be ramped up at 3-5° F/min up to 250° F and soaking at this temperature for 60 minutes at 40 psi pressure followed by a cooling rate of 8° F/min. Since the FM-73 adhesive and the boron/epoxy have the same curing cycles, the patches were co-cured in an Autoclave at a pressure of 45 psi. The patches were fabricated and applied to the aluminum panels by Integrated Technologies Inc. in Bothell Washington, under the direct supervision of the principal author. The nominal thickness of the adhesive film layer is 0.007 inch.

Figure 1: Specifications of an un-patched and patched aluminum specimen

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

3.1 Experimental Procedure

The fatigue tests were conducted on MTS 880 Material testing System with a maximum load capacity of 110,000 lbs. The tests were conducted at 10 Hz and 17.4 ksi under tension-

tension loading with a stress ratio (R) of 0.1. Four Digital Wave B-1025 broadband AE sensors with frequency response in the range 1 kHz – 1.5 MHz were used to detect AE waves. The sensors were placed at a distance of 1 inch on either side of the crack (Figure 2) and attached to the specimen with vacuum grease and electrical tape (Figure 3a).

Figure 2: AE transducer location for fatigue testing

The continuous increment in load in the tension-tension fatigue test makes it difficult to determine when the initiation of crack takes place and how and when the crack is propagating. An economic way of doing this is by employing special purpose crack propagation sensor. For this study, two crack propagation sensors were attached on the panels one each near the crack front with adhesive. The adhesive used was M Bond 610 adhesive. The adhesive was cured at a temperature of 325° F using a hot bonder. The crack propagation gage patterns consist of a number of resistor strands connected in parallel. When bonded to a structure, progression of a surface crack through the gage pattern causes successive open circuiting of the strands, resulting in an increase in total resistance. Two crack propagation gages model # TK-09-CPA01-005/DP (Vishay measurements group, Inc.) shown in Figure 3a, were mounted one each side of the crack and used to detect crack initiation and initial crack propagation. The fatigue tests were conducted on MTS 880 fatigue testing machine as shown in figure 3b.

Digital Wave VLF-UT/AE Acoustic Emission data acquisition system (Digital Wave Corp.) was used to acquire the AE data. AE waveforms were acquired at 25 MHz sampling rate using 4096 data points during the fatigue tests. The AE signals from the four sensors were passed through a pre-amplifier and pre-amplified at 24 dB then passed through the band pass filter set at 300 KHz and 5 MHz, respectively. The filtered signal was then passed through a signal conditioner unit where additional amplification of 24 dB was done. The trigger gain was set at 32 dB. The AE events were monitored and accurately located by using the Event detector. The total system gain was set at 80dB. The threshold was set at 100mV in order to filter out the noise signals that are far below the chosen threshold. A high-level signal output of voltage from the MTS 880 was fed to the acoustic emission system parameter channel and also digitized, this enabled viewing of the loading cycle of the MTS 880 and subsequently the elimination of events that occur in the lower part of the sine wave in loading that are not related to crack initiation and propagation. The acquired parameters and waveforms were stored in a computer for later processing and elimination of non-crack events. Figure 3b shows the fatigue test and the acoustic emission data acquisition setup. The fatigue tests generated between 5000 – 7000 waveforms. The analysis of

the data was carried out using WaveExplorer[®] software. The WaveExplorer[®] software runs the AE part and provides real time data acquisition and post-test data replay and analysis. Included in the software are noise check, wave check analysis tools, built-in theory for computing plate velocities and accurate source location. The AE signals were processed in time and frequency domain and analyzed to identify sensor features correlated with fatigue cycle and crack propagation. AE features such as AE event, energy, amplitude and frequency were investigated. The identified sensor features were used to develop neural network models for predicting crack propagation. Some methods of waveform filtering which are necessary for accurate crack propagation monitoring are presented.

3a: Attachment of AE sensors and crack propagation gages

3b: MTS 880 fatigue testing system and AE data acquisition setup

Figure 3: Experimental setup for fatigue testing and acoustic emission

3.2 Wave Propagation Theory

AE signals are digitized representations of high frequency stress waves setup in a medium when it undergoes some deformation like crack propagation. These stress waves are detected by piezo-electric sensors attached to the surface of the test object and are digitized and stored in a computer. Typical AE events have frequency content between 20 kHz – 5 MHz.

The dimensions and the material of the part under test contribute to the type of wave propagation that will occur. Two important factors determining the type of wave emanating from a structure during fatigue are 1) Type of Material, and 2) Velocity of Propagation. The wavelength λ , can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \quad (1)$$

where, c is the velocity of propagation and f is the frequency of the propagating disturbance.

3.3 Acoustic Emission Waveforms

Figure 4a shows a typical AE event emanating from a crack in 2024-T3 clad aluminum specimen and Figure 4b shows an AE event emanating from boron/epoxy composite matrix cracking as observed from the surface of the patch after failure. An AE event emanating from a crack growth is in extensional mode and once carefully analyzed the initial displacements on all four channels are all in the same direction. An extensional mode in an AE event appears at the

beginning of each wave and is characterized by 1) relatively smaller amplitude than the flexural mode and 2) a progression from lower frequency to higher frequency. A flexural mode in an AE event appears after the extensional mode, the frequency in this mode decreases as the wave propagates, and the amplitude is considerably larger than the extensional mode. The AE event (shown in Figure 4a) originating from crack growth in thin (0.063") aluminum specimen has a very high frequency content and is almost completely extensional. The AE event (shown in Figure 4b) seem to be originating from matrix cracking of composite patch is predominantly flexural in nature as the patch is located on the surface of the aluminum and has high frequency content compared to noise as it is emanating from cracking of a brittle material.

Figure 4: Typical waveform for crack events

3.4 Acoustic Emission Signal Processing and Noise Rejection

The basic approach to signal analysis for AE is to 1) reject the obvious noise signals due to mechanical noise (fretting) 2) apply location filter in order to filter out events taking place outside the expected area of event occurrence. 3) determine based on frequency content if the remaining signals could have been produced by sources of interest in this case crack propagation.

Analysis of the AE data was done on the WaveExplorer[®] software. After acquiring all the data the signals were subjected to some filtering techniques in order to get rid of the noise and other events. Noise signals cause saturation of the A/D board. If the signal voltage is greater than the range of the A/D converter, the A/D converter saturates and the signal is clipped. The result is a signal that has been significantly altered and is difficult to analyze. Figure 5 shows typical waveforms obtained from noise events due to A/D saturation.

Figure 5: Typical waveform for noise events

3.5 Event Source Location

One of the effective ways to filter out noise events is location filtering. All events that were outside the expected area of occurrence can be disregarded as noise. The waves being generated by crack growth and/or crack propagation are all within the specimen medium and hence are extensional waves. The front-end of the extensional waves is non-dispersive and hence

a low threshold is needed to trigger the front end of the extensional wave on which the source location calculations are performed. The noise events had been significantly reduced by applying 150 mV of threshold. The threshold was then dropped to 40 mV and the velocity of the waves set to 3018 m/s (825.13 inch/sec). The time of arrival are calculated using the Threshold crossing algorithm. On closer examination, one can find three different kinds of events.

- The events that are generated due to crack growth in aluminum. These have very high frequency content, and are almost completely extensional mode (Figure 4a).
- The events that are situated in the middle and show large flexural modes. These events are most probably generated due to the cracking of the repair or patch. As the patch is on the surface of the aluminum and is a brittle material, the waves that are associated with cracking of such material will have high frequency content and will produce large flexural modes (Figure 4b).
- The noise events that are scattered all over the spectrum, which have little or no frequency content (Figure 5).

3.6 Results and Discussion

The AE data was captured with a 100mV threshold to filter out as much mechanical noise as possible. A total of 6,499 AE events were recorded for the octagonal patch while 6624 events were recorded for the elliptical patch. All specimens were fatigued up to failure. Figure 6a, 6b, 6c, 6d show the plot of AE events and crack length versus the fatigue cycles for 5-ply octagonal and elliptical patches bonded with FM-73. It can be seen that there are regions of rapid and moderate AE activity. From the crack length vs fatigue cycles, Figure 6b and 6d, it is observed that AE increases with crack propagation. It can be seen in Figure 6 that near failure crack propagation becomes high. Correspondingly AE event increases considerably, showing a good correlation between crack propagation and AE event. The frequency was slowed down to 1 Hz to measure propagation of crack length. The crack length measurements were made visually. A 10% saturation filter was applied to the waveforms in order to filter out the noise events. The threshold was also increased to 150 mV. After the application of the saturation filter the total number of events for the octagonal patch was reduced to 6,290 while the number of events for the elliptical patch came down to 1,630, indicating that the majority of events recorded for the elliptical patch were noise events. After application of Location filtering the No of events in the case of octagonal patch reduce to 1,460 and those in the elliptical patch reduced to 926.

6a: AE event vs. fatigue cycles for 5-ply octagonal patch bonded with FM-73

6b: Crack length vs. fatigue cycles for 5-ply octagonal patch bonded with FM-73

6c: AE event vs. fatigue cycles for 5-ply elliptical patch bonded with FM-73

6d: Crack length vs. fatigue cycles for 5-ply elliptical patch bonded with FM-73

Figure 6: AE events vs fatigue cycle and crack length vs. fatigue cycle for octagonal and elliptical patches

Figure 7a and 7b show the AE source location after performing location filtering for the 5 ply octagonal and elliptical patches respectively. Almost all the events took place on or near the crack front indicating that the AE sensors were effective in detecting crack propagation.

7a: Results of AE source location for 5-ply octagonal patch bonded with FM-73

7b: Results of AE source location for 5-ply elliptical patch bonded with FM-73

Figure 7: Result of AE source location for octagonal and elliptical patch

Another criterion for differentiating crack signals from other signals is by examining the frequency content of the signal. Figure 8 shows the frequency content of noise waveforms for channel 1. The frequency of a noise waveform rapidly decays in a short period of time whereas crack waveforms as shown in Figure 9 have more uniform or flatter frequency response.

8a: FFT plot for a noise event

8b: FFT plot for noise event

Figure 8: FFT plots for noise events

9a: FFT plot for an extensional mode crack event

9b: FFT plot for a flexural mode crack event

Figure 9: FFT plots for crack propagation events

4. PREDICTING CRACK LENGTH WITH NEURAL NETWORKS

Cascade feed forward back-propagation neural network [4] was used to predict crack length based on the number of fatigue cycles and number of AE events. Figure 11 shows the architecture of a multi-layer feed forward neural network with one hidden layer and two inputs. A neuron with a scalar input vector, “p” and a scalar bias “b” is shown in the figure. The transfer function net input “n”, again a scalar, is the sum of the input “wp” and the bias “b”. This sum is the argument of the transfer function “f” given by:

$$n = \sum_{i=1}^p W_{i,p} P_i + b$$

The weights, “w” and bias “b” are both adjustable scalar parameters of the neuron. The central idea of neural networks is that such parameters can be adjusted so that the network exhibits some desired behavior.

Three separate networks were used to predict crack length; one network was used to predict the crack length from the number of fatigue cycles with 1-node, 4-nodes, and 1-node in the input layer, hidden layer, and output layers respectively (1x4x1 architecture); while the second was trained to predict the crack length from the number of AE events (1x4x1 architecture); and a third one was used to predict crack length from both fatigue cycles and AE events as inputs (2x4x1 architecture). All the networks were cascade feed forward networks with three fully connected layers. All networks had a Tan sigmoid function in the input layer, a Log sigmoid function in the hidden layer and a linear function in the output layer.

Figure 10: Architecture of a multi-layer feed forward network with two inputs

Back-propagation was created by generalizing the Widrow-Hoff learning rule to multiple layer network and non-linear differentiable transfer functions [4, 5]. Input vectors and the corresponding target vectors are used to train a network until it can approximate a function, associate input vectors with specific output vectors, or classify input vectors in an appropriate way as defined by the trainer..

Feed forward networks often have one or more hidden layers of sigmoid neurons followed by an output layer of linear neurons. Multiple layers of neurons with nonlinear transfer functions allow the network to learn nonlinear and linear relationships between input and output vectors. The linear output layer lets the network produce values outside the range -1 to $+1$. The Cascade feed forward network is similar to the standard feed forward network, however this is a fully connected network, which means that, the first layer has weights coming from the input, and each subsequent layer has weights coming from the input and all previous layers. All layers have biases. The last layer is the network output.

The training data for Network 1 consisted of 38 sets of input, 19 unknown inputs were also presented to the network. The inputs to the network were fatigue cycles and the output from the network was the crack length. For Network 2 the training set consisted of 62 inputs; 18 unknown inputs were also presented to the network. The inputs were the AE event number and the output from the network was the crack length. For Network 3 the inputs were fatigue cycle number and AE event number and the output was crack length. This network was trained on 57 sets of data and had 23 unknown inputs. All networks were trained to 500 epochs with the Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm.

Figure 11 shows the comparison of the measured and predicted crack length by neural network 1 that predicts the crack length from the number of fatigue cycles. The network was trained with 38 inputs, after training the network these training sets were presented to the network as inputs. The maximum percentage error was about $\pm 1.5\%$. Nineteen unknown inputs were also presented to the network, these were totally new inputs and the network had not been trained on these inputs before. The maximum percentage error was $+9\%$.

Figure 11: Measured and predicted crack length vs fatigue cycles for neural network 1

Figure 12: Measured and predicted crack length vs AE Events for neural network 2

Network 2 was used to predict the crack length based on the number of AE events. This network was trained on 62 data sets and was later presented with 18 unknown inputs. Figure 12 shows the comparison of measured and predicted crack length by neural network 2. It was found that the convergence of network 2 was much slower than Network 1 since the relationship between the AE events and crack length is highly non-linear. However the network was still able to predict the crack length based on the AE events with acceptable accuracy.

Figure 13a and 13b show the comparison of measured and predicted crack length by neural network 3. Network 3 predicted the crack length based on both the fatigue cycles and AE events as inputs. This network was trained on 57 data sets and was presented with 23 unknown inputs. This network was found to work really well in predicting the crack length and gave the most consistent results. The maximum percentage error was 1.2 % and -3.2 % respectively.

13a: Measured and predicted crack length vs fatigue cycles for neural network 3

13b: Measured and predicted crack length vs AE Events for neural network 3

5. CONCLUSIONS

A method for real-time monitoring and detection of crack propagation in adhesively bonded composite patch repair of cracked aluminum panels using Acoustic Emission has been developed and successfully demonstrated. A method for predicting crack propagation in the

patched panels using neural networks has also been developed and successfully demonstrated. Two 5-ply boron/epoxy panels namely an octagonal patch and an elliptical patch bonded to a cracked 2024-T3 aluminum panels were monitored with AE sensors while undergoing a fatigue test. From the results of the research the following conclusions can be made:

1. There is a correlation between AE events and crack propagation in cracked aluminum panels bonded with composite patch.
2. Use of multiple AE sensors is necessary for accurate source location and screening of non-crack related events like fretting, gripper noise and structural vibration.
3. Even at the high noise condition of 10 Hz loading the acoustic emission is capable of detecting crack propagation.
4. Noise signals can be differentiated from the signals originating from crack propagation by application of filtering techniques such as saturation, threshold and source location.
5. Crack propagation events in aluminum panels produce extensional waves which can be differentiated from matrix cracking events that produce flexural waves.
6. Noise signals have a lower frequency content, which sharply decays with time, while crack propagation signals have higher frequency content and a flatter frequency response.
7. It has been demonstrated that artificial neural networks can be used to accurately predict crack length from fatigue cycles and AE crack events. Three different neural network models have been successfully used to predict crack length with acceptable errors.

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